

Influence of Al substitution on the crystal structure and dielectric properties of $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_4\text{O}_{10+\delta}$ double perovskite

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Abstract

The complex perovskite related cobalt oxides have recently drawn considerable attention among the scientific community due to their interesting physical properties owing to their multiple valence states (1, 2). In the present study, we investigate the crystal structure and dielectric properties of Al substituted $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_4\text{O}_{10+\delta}$. The Co electronic configuration, primarily determined by the crystalline electric field created by first-neighbor oxygen ions, plays a central role in tuning the electronic properties of this compound. The parent compound under study is ferromagnetic and possesses high dielectric loss. Except ferrites, there are no magneto

Fig.1. XRD pattern of $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_{4-x}\text{Al}_x\text{O}_{10+\delta}$; $x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0$

dielectric materials with low dielectric loss. Hence it would be interesting to tailor the dielectric loss of $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_4\text{O}_{10+\delta}$ by substituting Co sites with Al ions. The compounds were synthesized via conventional solid state ceramic route. A detailed analysis of crystal structure using XRD and Raman spectra will be presented. $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_4\text{O}_{10+\delta}$ crystallize in $I4/mmm$ symmetry with lattice parameter of $a = b = 7.642 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 15.342 \text{ \AA}$. On substituting Co site with Al ions, the lattice parameters of the compounds are found to be increasing. The XRD patterns of $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_{4-x}\text{Al}_x\text{O}_{10+\delta}$; $x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0$; $\delta \leq 1$ is shown in Fig.1. The microstructure studies were also carried out using SEM. The dielectric properties of $\text{Sr}_3\text{YCo}_{4-x}\text{Al}_x\text{O}_{10+\delta}$; $x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0$; $\delta \leq 1$ were investigated and it was found that the compounds possess a large ϵ_r value in the order of 10^3 and $\tan \delta$ of the order of 10^{-1} .

Keywords: Perovskite, Raman spectra, Dielectric properties

References

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